

Colour of Complex-Diazoles. Part III. Reduced Pyrrole-Iminazole Compounds.

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In Part II of this series it has been pointed out by Chakravarti and Sen-Gupta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 830) that iminazoles derived from camphoric anhydride and aromatic diamines which contain reduced pyridine and iminazole rings condensed together in their molecules are colourless. Bistrzycki and Fässler (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1928, 6, 521), however, found that *o*-phenylene acetyl-1:3-benziminazole (IA) containing a partially reduced pyridine-iminazole skeleton was deep greenish-yellow in colour. But, although all of them contain reduced pyridine rings in the molecules, the camphor derivatives cannot be represented by any other alternative formulæ, whereas Bistrzycki and Fässler's compound admits of three different configurations:—

Formula (IC) represents a quinonoid structure and the colour of this compound may be attributed to this property of existing as tautomeric quinonoid and non-quinonoid structures (*cf.* Watson, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 29, 348; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 750). As regards the absence of colour in the camphor-iminazoles, Chakravarti and Sen-Gupta (*loc. cit.*) had suggested that this was not due to any hypsochromic effect of the camphor part of the molecule but might be due to the absence of a kind of unsaturated linkages like the

ortho- or *para*-quinonoid structures. These observations and some results obtained by us during the determination of the absorption spectra of several coloured and colourless complex iminazoles that are in progress in this laboratory for elucidating a relationship between their colour and constitution necessitated the investigation of similar reduced pyrrole and iminazole derivatives.

The simplest reduced pyrrole-iminazole was prepared by condensing succinic anhydride with *o*-phenylene diamine. Bistrzycki and Fässler (*loc. cit.*) failed to bring about this condensation. After several trials we found that the reaction could be brought about by following a method employed by Anderlini (*Gazzetta*, 1894, 24, 140). He appears to have obtained an additive compound $C_8H_4(NH_2)_2$, $C_2H_4O_3$ of m.p. 80° (decomp.) by mixing the anhydride and the diamine in cold benzene solution. This additive compound was supposed to be converted into an eight membered ring-compound *o*-phenylene succinyl-di-imide (II), m.p. 237° , on boiling the former either with benzene or absolute alcohol. We, however, could not isolate any additive compound having m.p. 80° , the first product of the reaction being invariably an acid imide, *o*-aminophenyl-amidosuccinic acid (III), m.p. $148-150^\circ$ (decomp.). The latter was converted into benzimidazole-2-propionic acid (IV), m.p. $225-226^\circ$, and not into the eight-membered ring-compound (II), by boiling with absolute alcohol.

Thiele and Falk (*Annalen*, 1906, 347, 112) made a similar observation in the case of an analogous product from phthalic anhydride and

o-phenylene diamine, which was proved to be identical with benzimidazole-2-*o*-benzoic acid of Bistrzycki (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1042) and therefore, did not contain an eight membered ring. Moreover, in a recent paper, Phillips (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2893) carried out the condensation between succinic acid and *o*-phenylene diamine in the presence of 4*N*-hydrochloric acid and obtained an acid of m.p.225°. We also prepared this compound by Phillips' method and confirmed its identity with our acid (IV) by a mixed melting point. The constitution of the acid (IV) is therefore established. The benzimidazole-2-propionic acid (IV) was then converted into (α : β)-dihydroacrylene-1:3-benzimidazole (V) by the usual methods.

Other reduced pyrrole-iminazoles were prepared by condensing hexahydrophthalic anhydride with aromatic diamines. For this condensation we needed hexahydrophthalic acid in quantity. We found, however, that the existing well-known methods for obtaining this compound (Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1890, 258, 198; Willstätter and Jaquet, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 770) gave very unsatisfactory yields. We, therefore, prepared platinum oxide according to the method of Voorhes and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1897) and used this catalyst for the reduction of phthalic acid. We further found that the use of 95% alcohol as the solvent facilitates this reduction.

By this method very good yields of hexahydrophthalic acid were obtained. The anhydride of this acid had m.p. 82° corresponding to the *cis*-variety. The anhydride was then condensed with *o*-phenylene, 1:3:4-tolylene and 1:2-naphthylene diamines in absolute alcoholic solutions. The products which were either acid or anils, or usually a mixture of both, were then converted into the condensed iminazoles by the ordinary methods. The reactions in the case of the *o*-phenylene diamine were as follows:—

From an analogy with the colourless reduced pyridine-iminazoles prepared by Chakravarti and Sen-Gupta (*loc. cit.*) from camphoric anhydride, it was anticipated that these reduced pyrrole-iminazole derivatives should come out as colourless compounds. This expectation has been realised and the iminazoles described in this paper have been obtained in beautiful colourless crystalline forms.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Aminophenylamidossuccinic Acid (III).—Succinic anhydride (5 g.) was suspended in 85 c.c. of hot dry benzene and to this was added *o*-phenylene diamine (5.4 g.) dissolved in 15 c.c. of benzene. The reaction was completed in a few minutes by shaking well, when a white pasty mass was deposited. This was separated and crystallised from alcohol in colourless silky needles, m.p. 148-150°, which are soluble in alkali carbonates, and in dilute acids, and give tests for primary amines. (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.5 per cent.).

Benziminazole-2-propionic Acid (IV).—*o*-Aminophenylamidossuccinic acid (5 g.) was boiled under reflux for three hours with 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The volume of the alcohol was reduced to one-third and allowed to stand when colourless prisms were deposited. They were crystallised from hot water in short colourless prisms which were soluble in alkali carbonates and strong acids; m.p. 225-226°. (Found: N, 14.90. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 14.74 per cent.). This compound was also prepared by Phillips' method (*loc. cit.*) and the mixed melting point was also 225°.

(α : β)-*Dihydroacrylene-1:3-benziminazole* (V).—Benziminazole-2-propionic acid (3 g.) was boiled under reflux with excess of acetic anhydride for half an hour. The excess of acetic anhydride was evaporated off. The residue was a sticky blackish mass which was purified by extraction with ether and hot benzene, when it gave a slightly dirty powder. This was dissolved in absolute alcohol and boiled with animal charcoal for two hours and after filtration the alcohol was removed. The residue was crystallised from nitrobenzene in colourless rosettes. From alcohol these come out as colourless silky needles, m.p. 172-175°. The crystals are insoluble in alkalis, but dissolve in concentrated acids. (Found: C, 69.48; H, 4.72; N, 16.43. $C_{10}H_8ON_2$ requires C, 69.76; H, 4.65; N, 16.27 per cent.).

This iminazole is also obtained by heating benziminazole-2-propionic acid at 230° for fifteen minutes and crystallising from alcohol.

Hexahydrophthalic acid.—Phthalic acid (10 g.), freshly precipitated from its sodium salt, was dissolved in 75 c.c. of 95% alcohol and was placed in a pressure resisting bottle. One gram of platinum oxide powder was added to the solution. The bottle was placed on a shaking machine, evacuated from air, and pure hydrogen was passed into the bottle under $2\frac{1}{2}$ atmospheric pressure till there was no more absorption. Then the catalyst was activated by removing the hydrogen, passing oxygen and shaking for five minutes, evacuating and finally passing hydrogen again. This process was repeated till there was no more absorption of hydrogen, the time necessary for the complete reduction being four hours. Finally oxygen was passed in order to cause the precipitate to settle. Hexahydrophthalic acid, m.p. 192-193° was obtained from the filtered solution in almost theoretical yield. This was converted into its anhydride and on crystallisation first from acetic anhydride and then from absolute alcohol gave m.p. 232° corresponding to the *cis*-variety.

Benzimidazole-2-hexahydro-o-benzoic Acid (VII).—Hexahydrophthalic anhydride (3 g.) was suspended in 30 c.c. of absolute alcohol and to it a solution of *o*-phenylene diamine (2 g.) in 20 c.c. of absolute alcohol was added. The mixture was refluxed for three hours on a water-bath. On cooling a precipitate came down, which was filtered off. The product was treated with a hot solution of sodium carbonate. A part of it went into solution which was filtered off from the residue (A). On acidification of the filtrate with concentrated, hydrochloric acid it gave a flocculent precipitate, which was washed with acetone and ether to remove colouring and soluble impurities. It was finally crystallised from nitrobenzene in colourless crystals, m.p. 245-247° with previous softening at about 200° (yield, 60 per cent). The compound is soluble in most solvents. (Found: N, 11.53. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.47 per cent.).

o-Aminohexahydrophthalanil (VI).—The residue (A) from the above experiment was crystallised from xylene when it gave colourless prismatic needles. Yield 90 per cent.; m.p. 195-196°. (Found: N, 11.52. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.47 per cent.).

Acetyl Derivative.—The anil was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and acetyl chloride was added to it drop by drop and the mixture was refluxed for about half an hour. When it was cooled a flocculent precipitate came down. It was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 261-263°. (Found: N, 9.61. $C_{16}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.79 per cent.).

(1': 2')-Hexahydrobenzoylene-1: 3-benzimidazole (VIII).—Benzimidazole-2-hexahydro-*o*-benzoic acid (5 g.) was heated under reflux with acetic anhydride (25 c.c.) for about an hour. Then the solution was poured into water and treated with an excess of sodium carbonate. The semi-solid pasty mass was purified like compound (V) and then crystallised from alcohol in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 175-176°. (Found: C, 74.29; H, 6.2; N, 12.85. $C_{14}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 74.84; H, 6.19; N, 12.89 per cent.).

*Ethyl Benzimidazole-2-hexahydro-*o*-benzoate*.—Hexahydrobenzoylene-1: 3-benzimidazole (2 g.) was made into a paste with a small quantity of absolute alcohol. A few drops of sodium ethylate solution were added and the mixture was boiled for half an hour. The clear solution was then poured into an excess of water. The ester which was precipitated crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless microscopic needles, m.p. 163-164°. (Found: C, 70.72; H, 7.09; N, 10.49. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires C, 70.58; H, 7.35; N, 10.89 per cent.).

o-Aminotolylamidohexahydrophthalic Acid.—*o*-Tolylene diamine hydrochloride (5 g.) was dissolved in 80 c.c. of absolute alcohol. To this were added a suspension of hexahydrophthalic anhydride (4 g.) in 20 c.c. of absolute alcohol and fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.). The mixture was heated under reflux for four hours. On cooling it was filtered from the sodium chloride residue. The filtrate was evaporated to half its bulk, when crystals were deposited, which were separated from the mother-liquor, treated with hot sodium carbonate solution and filtered from the insoluble residue (A).

The filtrate from (A) was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid till it was acidic to congo-red paper, when a small quantity of precipitate was obtained. This was crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 264-266°, which are insoluble in chloroform and ether, sparingly soluble in alcohol, but easily soluble in dilute acids, alkalis and alkaline carbonates. The yield of this acid is very low, being about 15 per cent. (Found: N, 10.01. $C_{15}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.15 per cent.).

o-Aminotolylhexahydrophthalimide.—The residue (A) described in the above experiment was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 274-276°. They are insoluble in ether and xylene but, soluble in acetone, alcohol, pyridine, ethyl acetate, etc. (Found: N, 10.67. $C_{15}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.85 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from dilute alcohol; m.p. 289-291°. (Found: N, 9.23. $C_{17}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.33 per cent.).

(1':2')-Hexahydrobenzoylene-1:3-ethylbenzimidazole.—*o*-Aminotolylhexahydrophthalimide was heated in a metal-bath at 280° till all the vapours had ceased to evolve and there was no more frothing. On cooling, the mass was extracted with absolute alcohol and then crystallised from it in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 186-187°. (Found: C, 74.84; H, 6.8; N, 11.81. $C_{15}H_{16}ON_2$ requires C, 75.00; H, 6.8; N, 11.67 per cent.).

Naphthimidazole-2-hexahydro-*o*-benzoic Acid.—The product from hexahydrophthalic anhydride (3 g.), 1:2-naphthalene diamine (3 g.) and 50 c.c. of alcohol was purified like compound (VII). The alkaline filtrate on acidification gave a precipitate which was crystallised from nitrobenzene in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 263-265°. They are insoluble in most solvents and also in dilute hydrochloric acid. Yield was about 70 per cent. (Found: N, 9.47. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.53 per cent.).

o-Aminonaphthylhexahydrophthalimide.—The residue from the above experiment was crystallised from xylene in colourless needles, m.p. 241-243°, which are soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and nitrobenzene, while insoluble in alcohol, acetone and carbon bisulphide. Yield 25 per cent. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.53 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 217-218°. (Found: N, 8.2. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.3 per cent.).

(1':2')-Hexahydrobenzoylene-1:3-naphthimidazole.—Naphthimidazole-2-hexahydro-*o*-benzoic acid was converted into the iminazole according to the method described for the compound (VIII). It crystallised from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 223-224°, which are sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene, xylene, nitrobenzene, etc. (Found: C, 78.76; H, 5.84; N, 10.17. $C_{18}H_{16}ON_2$ requires C, 78.63; H, 5.80; N, 10.22 per cent.).

